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QUARTZ VARIOMETER FOR MAGNETIC OBSERVATORIES

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INTRODUCTION

Quartz variometers (**QV**) have always differed markedly from other types of magnetometers in that they have significantly higher characteristics in terms of thermal stability, noise immunity and stable operation over a long period of time. This class of devices is designed to record and study geomagnetic variations. Most magnetic observatories (**MO**) of Russia, as well as many foreign observatories [1, 2], are equipped with such equipment.

In this paper, a new version of the magnetometer converter (**MMC**) [3] created on the basis of a compact design of a quartz magnetic sensor (**QMS**) and a photoelectric converter (**PEC**) is considered, and a version of the digital quartz variometer (**DQV**) created on the basis of this MMC is presented.

The proposed version of the QMS design is intended for modern magnetovariation stations (**MVS**), which are used for work in field and expeditionary conditions, as well as for special research and work in the magnetic observatory (**MO**) conditions.

QUARTZ VARIOMETER FUNCTIONAL DIAGRAM AND DESIGN

Fig.1 shows the functional diagram of the DQV, which is built on the basis of QMS and MMC. The same figure shows the general view (photo) of the QMS, as well as individual elements of the sensor and PET.

The MMC is a closed loop of negative feedback (**NF**) over a magnetic field (**MF**). This transformation is called an undercompensation transformation, since part of the magnetic signal remains uncompensated and the angle of the magnet rotation with the mirror is non-zero.

At the same time, the depth of the NF in this design of the MMC is approximately **1000**, which allows to achieve the maximum sensitivity of the device (with a dynamic range of **± 5000 nT**) of the order of **0.1 ... 0.01 nT**.

PEC

Fig.1. Functional diagram of the DQV and the general appearance of the QMS block design, - a suspension system with a quartz sensor and a PEC based on the TOC.

The functional circuit of the DQV (see **Fig. 1**) includes a circuit of converters connected in series: magnetic field/direct current, current/voltage, and voltage/digital code. QMS converts the MP variation into the angle of a magnetosensitive element (**MSE**) rotation. The optical sensor system (PEC) converts the rotation angle of the mirror reflector (**RM**) fixed together with the magnet on the quartz thread (**QT**) into a linear shift of the light spot, and the photodiode converts the linear shift of this light spot into a photocurrent. The first amplifier stage (**MDM**) linearly converts the photocurrent into voltage, and the second amplifier stage, - direct current amplifier (**DCA**), - amplifies the signal to the required value, after which the voltage from its output is linearly converted into a current, which is then converted by means of an NF coil into an MP, which almost completely (by about 0.999) compensates for the input signal.

From the output of the amplifier through the integrator circuit (**INT**), which includes a second-order low-pass filter with a cut-off frequency of **5 Hz** and an inverter, the signal enters to the analog-to-digital converter (**ADC**) circuit, where it is converted into a digital code. This digital code corresponding to the measured data from the output of the ADC goes to the input of the microcontroller (**MC**) and then (using the serial interface RS-232) to the personal computer (**PC**).

The MF/DC current converter is designed on the basis of QMS and PEC. The current/voltage converter is based on a direct current amplifier (DCA), and the voltage/digital code converter is based on an ADC.

MMC consists of the following main components - the QMS unit and the electronics unit (**EU**), which are powered from direct current (**SC**) source.

Functionally, the EU includes (see **Fig. 1**) schemes of MDM, DCA, ADC, control MC and power supply unit (**PS**). A network adapter (**NA**) or battery pack is used to power all DQV circuits. Also, the EU includes a control unit (**CU**) circuit and a temperature sensor (**TS**). DS is located near the QMS, which allows you to control the ambient temperature at the installation site of the quartz sensor.

The MC allows you to control the operation of all units both autonomously and with the help of an external PC.

Fig.1 shows the design of the individual elements of the QMS and PEC (top view) and a fragment of the suspension of the MSE on the QT. The QMS unit includes a quartz frame (**QF**) on which the MSE and the mirror reflector (RM) are fixed with the help of a QT, as well as coils of the initial installation (**IC**), feedback (NF) and calibration (**CC**) installed in the immediate vicinity of the MSE. Opposite the RM is a PEC, which is made on the basis of a transistor optocoupler (**TOC**) of the reflective type. TOC is a miniature photovoltaic converter of linear and angular displacements.

RM (size **2x4 mm**) is fixed on the QT and is located coaxially to the center of the PEC. In the proposed scheme, the RM is located at a distance of **10 mm** from the MSE. This allows to significantly reduce the influence on the MSE of the current source supplying the PEC circuit (in **Fig. 1** designated as SC). In this design of MMC, the PEC scheme of linear and angular movements is made on the basis of TOC type **AOT137A1** with an open optical channel [4].

The QMS unit is placed in a sealed rectangular metal non-magnetic housing with dimensions of **120x40x40 mm**, which is mounted using a ring nut on the platform (in Fig. 1 - not shown) with three alignment legs-screws for leveling the MSE in space. To connect to the EU, there is a 10-pin connector at the end of the QMS unit.

The EU circuit (see **Fig. 1**) includes a signal amplifier consisting of three functional units: a pre-amplifier (**MDM**), a DCA and an integrator (**INT**). The preliminary amplifier is made on the basis of a low-noise DCA with its own internal NF and MDM transformation.

The DCA provides the main amplification of the input signal from the PEC circuit. The DCA circuit together with the INT is made on the basis of the **OR497FS** chip and allows to achieve the required output level of analog voltage for the ADC, and also performs the functions of a filter with a cut-off frequency of **5 Hz**.

Thanks to the use of a special differential amplifier with MDM transformation in the MDM circuit (chip **ICL7653CSA**), it was possible to reduce (no more than **5 pT**) the own noise of the MMC and increase the overall stability of the DCA operation both in time and when the ambient temperature changes within wide limits.

At the same time, due to the environmental protection system, the dynamic range of measurement of geomagnetic variations is realized by the measuring channel of the MMC
± (1500... 6000) nT.

The 24-bit ADC (**AD7734** chip) provides analog voltage digitization from a INT output with a frequency of **16 Hz**. At the same time, the accuracy of MVS measurement is realized at the level of **0.1 nT** and more accurately.

The microcontroller (MC) is based on the **ATMEGA8** chip and transmits digital data from the ADC, exchanges information and control commands via the serial port (RS-232) from the PC. The MC activates all the work of the MMC, sends control commands related to the configuration and verification of the operability of the QMS to the control unit (CU).

The CU is made on the basis of a digital analog low-ohm controlled switch chip **ADG451**, the main purpose of which is the short-term inclusion of calibration current of various polarity in the windings of CC and IC during the *installation and calibration* of the MSE.

To one of the inputs of the MC through the serial interface is also connected TS, installed near the MSE and made on the basis of the chip **LM35DZ**. The TS consumes a current of not more than **60 μ A** and is structurally made in a plastic housing, which eliminates its influence on the MSE readings and controls the temperature inside the QMS with an accuracy of **$\pm 0.1^{\circ}\text{C}$** .

The PS unit is built using DC-DC converter type **DU1PO-12D05(N)**, which can be powered from an external DC source (or from a battery) with a voltage of **9... 15 V**, and from the standard NA voltage of **12±3 V**.

The PS supplies all electronic circuits of EU and PEC with the help of three stabilized SCs with a voltage of **±5 V** and **12 V**. At the same time, the power consumption of the DQV is not more than **1.5 ... 1.7 W**.

The created software for DQV provides the organization of a database of digital data, their visualization in the process of work in digital or analog form on a PC display.

All elements of the EU circuits are located in a non-magnetic metal metal waterproof housing measuring **240x165x55 mm** (not shown in **Fig. 1**), which is connected to the QMS unit using a shielded non-magnetic cable with a length of **3 m**.

CONCLUSION

As a result of the research and experimental work carried out, a new design of QMS and DQV based on it was created, while structurally the traditional elements of the QMS are compactly located in a small-sized rectangular non-magnetic case.

The MMC of the device has a fairly wide measuring range and a low level of its own noise of the measuring channel, the amplitude of which does not exceed **3...5 pT**.

Individual elements and electronic components of the EU (part of the MMC) are built according to a universal scheme, various versions of which were used in other similar developments of quartz MVS and magnetometers [5, 6].

The low energy consumption of the device circuit allows it to be effectively used in the design of *autonomous stations* powered by batteries or solar panels, which is important when conducting field research and geophysical work, as well as for the use of DQV in rarely serviced observation points.

The prototype of the created DQV passed laboratory tests in the Moscow observatory and showed satisfactory results.

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